

Observation on the six-eyed sand spider *Hexophthalma spatulatus* (Pocock, 1900) from South Africa (Araneae: Sicariidae)

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman¹, Joy Paton² & Linda Wiese³

¹ Project manager SANSA, dippenaaransie@gmail.com; ² SANSA Western Cape Team Member; ³ SANSA Eastern Cape Team Member

ABSTRACT: The six-eyed sand spider *Hexophthalma spatulatus* (Pocock, 1900) is a South African endemic that was described in 1900 as *Sicarius spatulatus* from Port Elizabeth in the Eastern Cape. They are free-living ground dwellers and one of the most distinctive features is their ability to blend into their sandy environment. The tufts of sickle-shaped setae on their abdomen and legs help in holding the sand covering in place. Based on photographs of live specimens, the general morphology of the species are discussed with notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation status.

Keywords: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), taxonomy

INTRODUCTION

Sicariidae specimens represented by two genera *Hexophthalma* and *Loxosceles* have been sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). *Hexophthalma* Karsch, 1879 is represented by eight species and four of the species are known from South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2025).

They are free-living ground dwellers, known as the six-eyed sand spiders, and are usually covered in sand particles, making them cryptic against their background (Duncan *et al.*, 2007). They can stay motionless for long periods beneath the soil surface, waiting for prey (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021).

Hexophthalma spatulatus (Pocock, 1900) is a South African endemic species described in 1900 as *Sicarius spatulatus* from Port Elizabeth. In the First Spider Atlas (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010) seven localities from two provinces were sited. The species has since been recorded from 18 localities in two provinces (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021).

The most remarkable characteristic of members of *Hexophthalma* is their cryptic appearance and behaviour. The dry soil particles adhere to special body setae bearing fine hair (Duncan *et al.*, 2007; Magalhaes *et al.*, 2017). Two types of body covering have been observed. Some species have a higher density of body setae with multiple rows of macrosetae on the lateral border of the carapace, prolateral setae on the femora, and abdomen giving them a 'dirtier' appearance compared to the 'cleaner' species. Observations showed that the 'dirtier' species are more cryptic and tend to remain motionless on the soil, while the 'cleaner' species cover themselves with sand particles disappearing below the surface (Duncan *et al.*, 2007).

Hexophthalma spatulatus is one of the 'dirtier' species and is covered with a dense layer of sand particles (Figs 1 & 2). In this paper, the general morphology of the species is discussed based on observations of live specimens, with notes on their colour variation, general behaviour, conservation status, and distribution in South Africa.

METHODS

The voucher specimens sampled during SANSA surveys are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida of the Agricultural Research Council in Pretoria. Photographs were also requested for the SANSA Virtual Museum, and photographs of *Hexophthalma spatulatus* from several localities have been received (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

Figures 1–2. *Hexophthalma spatulatus*. 1. Female from Blue Hill Escape Nature Reserve. 2. Female from Addo Elephant National Park. Credits: 1. Joy Paton. 2. Linda Wiese.

Figures 3–10. *Hexophthalma spatulatus*. 3. Male body dorsal view. 4. Eye pattern. 5. Setae on abdomen. 6. Femora enlarged scoop-shaped seta. 7–8. Male palp. 9–10. Spermathecae. Credits: 3–5, 8–9. A. Dippenaar-Schoeman. 6–7, 10. After Magalhães *et al.*, 2013.

TAXONOMY

Hexophthalma spatulata (Pocock, 1900)

Sicarius spatulatus Pocock, 1900: 321 (mf); Newlands, 1986: 56; Lotz, 2012: 10.

Hexophthalma spatulata Magalhães, Brescovit & Santos 2017: 853; Lotz, 2018: 14; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021: 10; 2023: 360.

Diagnosis: Size: Total length 8–9 mm. Carapace flat, as wide as long; narrower in eye region; integument hard, coriaceous; six eyes in two rows, in three diads (Fig. 4). Abdomen markedly depressed, clothed in sickle-shaped curved setae (Figs 3–5). Legs laterigrade; stout with two claws with several serrated bristles born on a small onychium; legs clothed in sickle-shaped setae; femora with enlarged scoop-shaped setae (Fig. 6) dorsally raised on a slight mound. Haplogyne spiders; male embolus with a broad, blunt apex (Figs 7 & 8); female spermathecae consist of numerous copulatory tubes; opening directly into epigastric furrow (Figs 9 & 10). Males resemble females, but their legs are longer, spanning up to 30 mm.

Colour variation: Specimens preserved in alcohol are very dark grey (Fig. 11). *Hexophthalma spatulatus* is one of the 'dirtier' species and the colour of specimens photographed depends on the colour of the sand particles adhering to their bodies (Figs 2 & 12).

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Alicedale (-33.31, 26.08); Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Port Alfred (-33.58, 26.89); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72). **Western Cape:** Borrelfontein, 8 km W of Gouritz Mouth (-34.33, 21.85); Hermanus (-34.4, 19.25); Bredasdorp (-34.53, 20.04); Caledon (-32.4, 19.43); Piketberg (-32.90, 18.755); Swellendam, Tradouws Pass (-33.95, 20.7); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Van der Kemps Kloof (-33.876, 25.454); Kammanasie Nature Reserve (-33.66, 23.12); N of Mosselbay (-34.010, 22.056); Blue Hill Escape Nature Reserve (-33.583, 23.438)*; Bereaville Riviersonder end Nature Reserve (-34.039, 19.493)*; Gondwana Game Reserve SE Herberstsdale (-34.07, 21.9); Willowmore (-33.3, 23.5)*; Paternoster (-32.81, 17.89)*

* From iNaturalist

LIFESTYLE

Hexophthalma spatula has been sampled by hand and in pitfall traps, mainly from the Fynbos and Thicket Biomes (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024) in the Eastern and Western Cape. One of their most distinctive features is their remarkable ability to blend into their sandy environments. In their natural habitat, they face threats from larger predators, including birds, reptiles, and mammals. As predators they play a critical role in keeping the insect and arachnid populations in check, ensuring a balanced ecosystem.

Hexophthalma spatula, with its dense layer of setae, catches a thick layer of soil particles to the cuticle (Fig. 11). This helps to conceal the spider, resulting in them remaining motionless on the soil surface, moving only when molested (Duncan *et al.*, 2007). During mating the males are more active and aggressive, roaming around searching for a mate.

Figures 11–12. *Hexophthalma spatulatus* female. 11. Alcohol material. 12. Live female from Blue Hill Escape Nature Reserve. Credits: 11. ASD. 12. Joy Paton.

Simon (1899) first noted their unusual cup-like egg cocoon, covered with sand, and usually attached to the substrate. Information on the burying behaviour of members of *Hexophthalma* appears in Reiskind (1965), while Levi (1967) reported on their predatory and sexual behaviour and Levi & Levi (1969) on their sexual behaviour and the construction of the egg cocoon.

Species of *Hexophthalma* have also raised interest because of their supposed medical importance. Laboratory studies in South Africa by Newlands (1982), Newlands & Atkinson (1988) and Van Asweger et al., (1997) have shown that *Hexophthalma* bites cause severe ulcerating lesions and death in laboratory animals. Bites by *Hexophthalma* spp. are uncommon and according to Müller et al. (2012) clinical evidence is inconclusive.

CONSERVATION STATUS

The species has a wide distribution it is known from both sexes and is listed as Least Concern. The species is protected in Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al., 2020); De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009); Kammanasie Nature Reserve; Blue Hill Escape Nature Reserve; Bereaville Riviersonder end Nature Reserve and Gondwana Game Reserve.

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